

Preliminary Assessment of PRATIC Start-Up Core Neutronics Benchmark at Beginning Of Cycle-Hot Zero Power

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents some preliminary results obtained in the framework of the EASI-SMR/WP7 EU-funded project. The paper focuses on the PRATIC core, a soluble boron-free light water small modular reactor core of the pressurized water type. The simulations were conducted at hot zero power conditions to prioritize the neutronic effects during the initial phase of the benchmark. The results obtained by 8 partners, with 7 calculation codes and two nuclear data libraries, are presented in this paper. The reference results are obtained using the SERPENT-2 Monte Carlo code, and all other results obtained using Monte Carlo or deterministic methods are compared against this reference. An in-depth analysis of the deviations from the reference still needs to be carried out, but these preliminary results allow us to develop some hypotheses about the origin of the deviations and draw some initial conclusions, in order to calibrate the neutron results of all partners and move forward with confidence to the next phase of the project: benchmarking under full hot power conditions.

Keywords: EASI-SMR; Monte Carlo; Determinist; Static Simulations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Launched in 2024 under the Horizon Europe Euratom Programme (2024–2028), the EASI-SMR (Ensuring Assessment of Safety Innovations for Small Modular Reactors) project addresses technical, safety and licensing challenges of European light-water SMRs. Organized into nine Work Packages (WP), the project includes advanced core physics studies on boron-free SMR designs in WP7, aiming to enhance understanding of their neutronic behavior and validate industrial analysis tools in normal and off-normal operation [1]. This paper focuses on the PRATIC [2] core study and on the first phase of task 7.2 dedicated to the benchmarking of neutron calculations under hot zero power (HZP) and beginning of cycle (BOC) conditions. The objective of this phase is to calibrate the neutron tools in relation to each other. As a reminder, Task 7.1 of WP7 was devoted to the specifications of the PRATIC core and was the subject of document [3].

2. CALCULATION ROUTES

This part of the document outlines the calculation methods employed by 8 partners of the EASI-SMR / WP7 project, issued from 5 European countries, to contribute to the benchmarking process. It is divided in two sections: codes based on Monte Carlo method (2 routes), and deterministic codes (5 routes).

2.1. Simulations Based on Monte Carlo Method

2.1.1. Reference results: SERPENT-2 code

KIT provided the reference results for the PRATIC benchmark, but other partners gave their help to confirm this reference (HZDR, ASNR and PSI). Serpent code v2.1.32 [4], developed by VTT, was utilized to perform both 2D reflective lattice and 3D full-core calculations. Geometry and material specifications were taken from the PRATIC reference documentation [3]. Nearly default settings were used for both assembly-lattice and core models. For the 2D lattice, one-eighth symmetry was considered using the *usym* card, while the core was modelled without symmetry considerations.

Results were obtained using ENDF/B-VII.1 [5] and JEFF-3.1.1 [6] nuclear data libraries (NDLs) obtained from the SERPENT data repository. In both cases, all cross sections were set to a fixed temperature of 600 K (.06c), and no Doppler broadening was needed. For the thermal scattering law of H in H₂O, ENDF/B-VII.1-based solutions were evaluated exactly at 600 K, whereas for JEFF-3.1.1-based solutions, an interpolation (*therm* card) was applied using libraries at 574 K (.11t) and 624 K (.13t). Additionally, unresolved resonance probability table sampling was enabled (set *ures* 1).

For the criticality source mode simulations, the 2D assembly cases were run using 10⁶ neutron histories with 1000 active and 100 inactive cycles. The full 3D core simulations used 2×10⁶ particles with 2000 active and 500 inactive cycles. With these statistics, the 1 σ uncertainty in the infinite and effective multiplication factors remained below 3 pcm.

2.1.2. TRIPOLI-4®

TRIPOLI-4® is a Monte Carlo radiation transport code developed by the French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (CEA). The role of the TRIPOLI-4® calculations in WP7 of the EASI-SMR project is to demonstrate how sensitive the results are to different types of Monte Carlo codes,

which are considered to be free of modelling bias. TRIPOLI-4® calculations were carried out by CEA and EDF using version 4.12.1 of the code, with JEFF-3.1.1 evaluation for both, and ENDF-B/VII.1 for CEA only. Linear interpolation of cross sections between two tabulated temperature was necessary only for JEFF-3.1.1 because the 600 K value does not exist. Both CEA and EDF used an option that permits to limit the use of the ‘Sampling of the Velocity of the Target nucleus’ (SVT) algorithm up to 4.95 eV at most. This option was introduced to maximize consistency between the results obtained from TRIPOLI-4® and APOLLO3®.

2.2. Simulations Based on Deterministic Method

2.2.1. CMS5 (CASMO5 / SIMULATE5)

The CMS5 code package (Core Management System version 5) is a suite of software tools developed by Studsvik Scandpower for simulation of light water reactors (LWRs). CASMO5 [7] and SIMULATE5 [8] are the two main components of the CMS5 package. CASMO5 is a lattice physics code that performs detailed 2D transport calculations using the Method of Characteristics (MOC) in a fine energy-group structure, then condenses the cross sections into a coarser energy mesh. SIMULATE5 is a 3D core simulator that uses macroscopic cross-section data from CASMO5 to perform core-wide neutronic and thermal-hydraulic calculations.

For the purpose of the PRATIC start-up benchmark at HZP, in order to determine the optimal modeling setup, several sensitivity analyses were performed by the partners to assess the effect of different modeling options on accuracy. At KIT, all lattice simulations were performed with ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data [5] using the P3 approximation for the anisotropic scattering and a 19-group energy structure, neglecting thermal expansion [9].

The same options were used at ASNR for the lattice simulations. The homogenized cross-section files were generated using the S5C card, with the “TDN” option, enabling branches where moderator temperature and density are decoupled. This was selected to remain consistent with the standard application of the code for reactor cycle modeling. However, this approach introduces interpolation effects in cross-section data. Both the ENDF/B-VII.1 and JEFF-3.1.1 [6] libraries were employed at ASNR.

At PSI, instead of using “TDN” card, fixed moderator number density and material temperature are specified in the material card to decouple the moderator temperature and density. Calculations were performed using P3 approximation, 95 energy groups, with ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data.

The SIMULATE5 models of the PRATIC core were slightly different: ASNR and KIT chose to perform full 3D core diffusion calculations with a 4-group energy structure, when PSI modelled a quarter 3D core, with 8-group. Radial reflectors were modeled using a 2D approach at KIT and PSI, and 1D at ASNR.

2.2.2. HELIOS / DYN3D

HELIOS [10] is a deterministic neutron and gamma transport code (Studsvik Scandpower) used in this project with version 1.10, relying on ENDF/B-VI nuclear data libraries. This deviates from benchmark specifications with regard to the defined nuclear data libraries (NDLs) ENDF/B-VII.1 or JEFF-3.1.1. It applies the intermediate resonance (IR) method for self-shielding of homogeneous systems and the

subgroup method for heterogeneous ones. The neutron transport calculation was carried out using the current coupling and collision probabilities (CCCP) method with a 190-group library.

DYN3D code is developed for investigations of transients in cores of thermal power reactors with hexagonal or quadratic fuel elements [11]. In the PRATIC start-up benchmark analysis at HZP, the model used is based on a two-group diffusion approximation and a nodal expansion method.

2.2.3. APOLLO3®

APOLLO3® is a deterministic reactor code used for lattice and core calculations, developed at CEA with the financial and technical support of EDF and Framatome since 2007 [12]. CEA has used this code with the JEFF-3.1.1 and ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data libraries (NDLs), and the SHEM-MOC scheme [13], which is a reference for the treatment of BWR and PWR lattice calculations. Self-shielding is evaluated using a 281-group energy mesh. Then the neutron flux is calculated using the Method of Characteristics (MOC) and the P3 approximation for the anisotropic scattering, then finally condensed at two groups. Lattice-core equivalence coefficients allow the correct accuracy of the reaction rates to be propagated from the lattice to the core stage, despite this condensation. Core calculations are realized using a 2-group pin-by-pin diffusion model using the MINOS solver.

2.2.4. WIMS / PANTHER

The nuclear constants for fuel and reflector constituents of the EASI-SMR PRATIC core, are generated by means WIMS (Winfrith Improved Multigroup Scheme) 10 ru2 and the ENDF/B VII.1 library of microscopic data. The neutron transport problem is solved by means of a method of characteristics in 2D considering 22 subgroups of neutrons, subsequently condensed to 2-group, homogenized constants in infinite medium. PANTHER is a few-group neutron diffusion reactor code distributed by ANSWERS. The flux distribution is calculated using a nodal method on a coarse 3D mesh. The fine-grained power distribution is accessible through pin power reconstruction. Core simulations of the PRATIC benchmark are performed with PANTHER 5.6.6 on a single assembly model with 4 planar nodes per channel. Neutron scattering is considered with a P0 “isotropic” approximation.

2.2.5. CASMO5 / PARCS

In addition to the CMS5 analyses, ASNR performed simulations with the CASMO5/PARCS code sequence. CASMO5 provided homogenized two-group cross sections to the PARCS [14] 3D diffusion code for full-core steady-state calculations. The same modeling parameters as in the CMS5 setup were used (PN order 3, 19-group MOC step, 1D radial reflector), with the exception of activating the fundamental mode option. Cross sections were generated using the same case matrix as for CMS5. In PARCS, the neutron mesh was defined with a 2x2 radial node structure per fuel assembly and 20 axial nodes in the fuel region, complemented by two nodes in each axial reflector. Calculations were performed using both ENDF/B-VII.1 and JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data libraries.

3. COMPARISON WITH THE REFERENCE

All results in this section are compared with the reference ones (i.e., results obtained with SERPENT-2 by KIT, cf. Section 2.1.1).

3.1. Multiplication Factor of Fuel Assemblies in Infinite Lattice

The PRATIC startup core includes five fuel assembly types, modeled in infinite lattice with eleven configurations based on the presence of grey, black, or no control rods. Simulations are at zero burnup, 600 K for cross sections, and 300°C for geometries/densities, using 2D reflective boundaries without neutron leakage. Results are grouped into six families, and differences from the SERPENT-KIT reference are averaged within each family for summary. Results obtained with ENDF/B nuclear data libraries are shown in Figure 1, and those obtained with JEFF-3.1.1 are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Deviations of K_{∞} values from the reference, evaluated using ENDF-B/7.1 or 6.0.

Figure 2. Deviations of K_{∞} values from the reference, evaluated using JEFF-3.1.1.

Monte Carlo simulations using TRIPOLI-4® and SERPENT-2 with the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library show excellent agreement across all configurations, with deviations not exceeding 50 pcm. However, when using the JEFF-3.1.1 library, especially for configurations with many gadolinium pins, deviations reach up to 250 pcm (EDF) and 110 pcm (CEA). The cause of this discrepancy between the two TRIPOLI-4® datasets is under investigation. Both codes interpolate cross sections for temperature, but ENDF/B-VII.1 provides the thermal scattering law (TSL) for ^1_0H in H_2O at exactly 600 K, while JEFF-3.1.1 only offers it at 574 K, necessitating interpolation. The default approach for neutron scattering treatment in TRIPOLI-4® is using the thermal scattering law (TSL, also known as “ $S(\alpha, \beta)$ ”) below 4.95 eV if it exists, then the SVT model up to 20.68 eV, and the Asymptotic Kernel (AK) model above [15]. To align with APOLLO3®, the SVT model was deactivated in TRIPOLI-4® calculations, potentially underestimating thermal scattering and contributing to differences with SERPENT 2.

Deterministic calculations generally agree well with SERPENT-2, with APOLLO3® and CASMO5 results mostly within [-100; +100] pcm. However, CASMO5 calculations carried out by PSI show larger deviations, currently under investigation. WIMS10 results from Tractebel deviate due to using 574 K instead of 600 K for cross sections. HELIOS results from SSTC-NRS differ more significantly, likely because they use the older ENDF/B-VI library.

In conclusion, the choice of nuclear data library and the handling of thermal scattering laws and temperature interpolation are crucial for accurate results. Adherence to benchmark specifications and the use of the same nuclear data are essential for minimizing discrepancies and ensuring consistency across different codes and institutions.

3.2. Control Rod Worth

The control rod worth (CRW)—the reactivity difference between rod-inserted and All-Rods-Out configurations—was evaluated by partners using ENDF/B-VII.1, ENDF/B-VI.0, or JEFF-3.1.1 libraries, then compared to SERPENT-2. Relative deviations (Δ CRW) are shown in figures 3 and 4. Calculations use the same conditions as previously (zero burnup, 600 K cross sections, 300°C geometries/densities), but results are now from 3D core simulations.

Monte Carlo results show excellent agreement, with all relative deviations for both nuclear data libraries (NDLs) within $\pm 0.5\%$. Deterministic codes' control rod efficiency deviations from the SERPENT-2 reference fall within [-10; +7] %, with APOLLO3® and CMS5 staying under 3%. APOLLO3® slightly overestimates, while CMS5 underestimates rod efficiency, though both remain close to the reference. The largest deviations for these codes occur with the G2 group, which has the lowest efficiency (around -1000 pcm), compared to other groups (from -1500 for G4 to -33000 pcm for ARI). CASMO/PARCS and WIMS/PANTHER systems show slightly higher deviations, peaking at -10% for the G4 configuration—a black control rod (24 Ag-In-Cd rods), unlike G1–G3 grey clusters (8 Ag-In-Cd + 16 steel rods). Geometry or material errors are ruled out, as the same lattice model (CASMO) is used to feed PARCS and SIMULATE core calculations carried out by ASNR. Discrepancies observed in PARCS and PANTHER likely stem from differing calculation models and options compared to APOLLO3® and CMS5, currently under investigation. DYN3D results, using ENDF/B-VI.0, remain consistent with others, within [-1; +7] %. Overall, all codes demonstrate good agreement, with minor variations attributed to specific configurations and modeling choices.

Figure 3. Relative deviations of Control Rod Worth from the reference, evaluated with ENDF-B/7.1 or 6.0.

Figure 4. Deviations of Control Rod Worth from the reference, evaluated with JEFF-3.1.1.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the status of the PRATIC core benchmark, involving nine partners from six countries and realized within the framework of Work Package 7 of the European EASI-SMR project. Not all results from all partners could be presented here for the sake of brevity. Furthermore, these results are preliminary, and the conclusions or hypotheses stated are not definitive, as a verification stage is still required. These results demonstrate that although the configurations were selected in the HZP and BOC states with well-defined materials and geometries, deviations from the reference obtained using the SERPENT-2 Monte Carlo code can range from one to several hundred pcm for the reactivity of assemblies modeled as an infinite lattice, and from 0 to 10% for the efficiency of control rods evaluated using core calculations. In the next part of this benchmark, we will analyze the remaining results obtained under HZP conditions, such as power distributions, temperature coefficients, and kinetic parameters. Then, we will perform new simulations under HFP conditions.

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